

RDM goes OER

Community-Sourcing a
Canadian Open Educational Resource
on Research Data Management

Presented by Liz Hill and Kristi Thompson
Western Libraries, Western University

Research Data Management in the Canadian Context

A Guide for Practitioners and Learners

Edited by: Kristi Thompson, Elizabeth Hill and Emily Carlisle-Johnston (English)
Danielle Dennie and Émilie Fortin (French)

Background

Pandemic discussion groups

The Need

“I developed a three-credit graduate course Managing Research Data (INFO 6290) for the Dalhousie School of Information Management in 2017. Feedback from students taking the course in 2021 is that the current textbook is out-of-date and of limited relevance to the Canadian context, but there are no obvious alternatives.”

Formation of the
RDM-OER list and
community.

Zoom!

The English editors

- List: much discussion, no textbook writing
- Settled on an OER - RDM is committed to open data, so open text seemed like a good fit
- Idea of an edited collection, with experts writing about specific topics, came up
- Formation of the original Editorial Triumvirate: Emily Carlisle-Johnston, Elizabeth Hill, Kristi Thompson

First steps

- Roughed out a list of topics with volunteers to write them
- Threw this away and created a Call For Proposals
- Realized that we are in Canada...

Canada (is really big)

- French is first language of majority (Quebec) or significant minority (New Brunswick)
- Official languages are English, French and Inuktut
- English is first language of majority (rest of Canada)

The French editors

We put out a call and were very fortunate to have Danielle Dennie and Émilie Fortin join us.

They joined the overall project group and took on French communication, editing and review, as well as oversight of the French edition

Funding equity

Good intentions aren't enough

“There is huge deficit of French resources... Which is a big issue for OER especially, since a lot of our French students at uOttawa have to pay more for course materials than anglo students because OER resources don't exist.”

Finance

- Translation costs money
- No, more money than that. A lot of money.
 - Plus tax.
- Copyediting (in two languages!) is also expensive.
- Total estimated cost: ~\$45,000 CAD

FUNDING FOR TRANSLATION AND COPYEDITING

Decolonization

- Canada's Indigenous Peoples (First Nations, Inuit and Metis) have not always been treated well by researchers or Canada's government, leading to mistrust and a need for a different relationship
- They have responded by taking leadership on developing research protocols, including for data
 - “Nothing about us without us”
 - Ownership, Control, Access and Possession – OCAP®
- Recruited panel of indigenous authors to contribute

Communication

- News updates
- Translation
- Timeliness
- Status

Balancing act

- So many parts / roles
 - Copy editor
 - Project manager
 - Translation
 - Grant funding

Community buy-in is invaluable... insularity is not

- Positive response from peer reviewers
- Support applying for grants
- Public pressure of bodies that initially did not award us money
- Need to reach beyond our community to make the text inclusive and comprehensive

~~Spring 2022~~

~~Fall 2022~~

Summer 2023

~~Spring 2023~~

By the numbers

- 2 languages
- 5 Editors
- About 25 peer reviewers
- 39 Authors from across Canada (Newfoundland to BC!) including librarians, teaching faculty and statisticians
- \$44,410 in funding

Research Data Management in the [Your Context Here]

Take our OER and make it
your own!

Why adapt our OER?

- Open Educational Resources (including textbooks) are publicly available online, free to use, and have open licenses that allow them to be redistributed and, often allow them to be adapted or revised
- Ours is published under a CC-BY-NC - allows for adaptation for non-commercial purposes so long as original creators are attributed
- Why adapt our OER?
 - Because you can!
 - Open texts reduce barriers for students
 - Open texts are useful for practitioners
 - Much of the material is not Canada-specific: change as much or as little as you want

Material coverage

- Ensuring ~~good~~ any coverage of essential topics (and what's essential?) turned out to be one of our challenges
- For example, DMPs are one of the first things people learn about in connection to RDM, but nobody volunteered to write the “this is a basic DMP” chapter
- Originally planned a couple of pages at the beginning for definitions and a data lifecycle diagram to open the book.
- This plan was revised as we found other things that needed to be defined, diagrammed or explained... until we gave up and just wrote another chapter

An introductory-level intro

- Need to step back and think of what was needed to make the book accessible to a hypothetical person who knows nothing about data
- Define Research Data Management
 - Define research data
 - Define data... what does a data file even look like?
 - Added a section on how to structure a data file
- Explain national policy on RDM
 - Why is there a policy? Why are data sharing requirements needed?
 - Added a callout explaining the replication crisis
 - Who made this policy? Is it a law? If not why care?
 - Added a section explaining funding agencies

Proposed titles

- Introduction to RDM and the Data Lifecycle
- Introduction to RDM, DMPs and the Data Lifecycle
- RDM: Lifecycle, DMPs, Data Sharing and the Tri-Agency Policy
 - And what does a data file look like...
- RDM: WTF?
- Settled on...
The Basics: An Introduction to Research Data Management

General notes

- All chapters start with an introduction explaining what the chapter covers and a set of learning outcomes, and finish with reflective questions or exercises (sometimes both).
- We've made an attempt to define all specialized or unfamiliar terms and link them
- Callouts are used in places to illustrate concepts or provide additional, nonessential information
- Most chapters are intended to stand alone (once you have the basics down)
- A guiding principle of our book is that RDM always happens in a context and for a purpose.
 - A corollary: there is no perfect RDM, just RDM that is good enough for a specific purpose.

Sections of the OER

- Front matter (Foreword and acknowledgements)
- First Principles
- A Canadian Context for RDM
- Working with Data
- Considering Types of Data
- Perspectives on Research Data Management

First Principles in Research Data Management

- The Basics: An Introduction to RDM
 - Can keep most, edit or remove policy or regulation-specific information, add anything you think should be included. This is the kitchen sink (or maybe dishwasher) chapter.
- The FAIR Principles and Research Data Management
 - Can be used as-is
- Indigenous Data Sovereignty
 - Applies specifically to Canadian First Nations; use for inspiration

A Canadian Context for Research Data Management

- A driving principle of our book is that RDM always happens in a context. This section is about that context.
- History and Landscape
 - Looks at development of national and regional players in Canadian RDM. Can't be reused but you might want to write something similar
- Research Data Sharing and Reuse in Canada: Practice and Policy
 - This talks about funder policies and requirements, and national infrastructure and resources.
- RDM Maturity Assessment Model in Canada
 - How to assess an institution. Can probably be adapted to other maturity assessment models without much difficulty

Working With Data and Types of Data

- This is the most technical part of the book and can be reused largely as is. These sections could probably be an RDM course on their own – it's what many practitioners think about when they think of teaching RDM.
- Two data cleaning chapters: Discuss data errors, cleaning exercises in OpenRefine, Excel and R
- Formats and Metadata, Active Data Curation, Digital Preservation
- Qualitative, Quantitative and Geospatial
- Sensitive Data theory and practice
 - Partly technical (reuse as is) partly talks about applicable Canadian regulations

Perspectives on RDM

- This section contains a couple of philosophical chapters that critique the field of RDM
- These are perspectives – use as starting points for discussion, reuse, remix!
- Could be expanded – e.g. we wanted more international coverage

Today Canada, tomorrow
RDM OER WORLD DOMINATION!

Coming soon!

Reach out if you have questions or want a look.

Liz Hill, ethill@uwo.ca

Kristi Thompson, kthom67@uwo.ca

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